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TRAINING BACK PROPAGATION ALGORITHM TO DESIGN MICRO STRIP PATCH ANTENNA

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Abstract:

This paper discuss about the training of back propagation algorithm for designing a micro strip patch antenna. Here we have taken the design parameters of a patch antenna and calculated resonant frequency. Then we trained back propagation algorithm to calculate resonant frequency by giving the patch parameters as inputs to the algorithm. We compared calculated, trained and tested data frequencies and a good agreement is obtained between them.

Key words—Micro stripPatch Antenna; Knowledge Based Neural Network (KBNN); Resonant Frequency;

I. INTRODUCTION

Neural networks have recently drawn significant attention as powerful tools in artificial intelligence (AI) research [1]-[4]. Their structural and behavioral resemblance to systems of biological neurons has also proved useful in a wide variety of engineering applications [5] [6]. In this paper, we wish to exploit the advantages using neural networks for micro strip patch antenna designs. An extensive literature was devoted to approximating an unknown mapping related to a circuit performance, in between or beyond the limited sampling points, by the curve-fitting techniques. This allows us to quickly calculate the output values at any arbitrary input points. In the curve-fitting techniques, the specific form of a function to be fitted to data is first chosen and then fitting according to some error criterion (such as the least mean of squared errors) is carried out. The functional form should be sufficiently general so as to approximate large classes of mappings which might arise in practice.

The commonly used fitting functions include polynomials, rational functions and trigonometric functions. A primary advantage of neural networks over the curve fitting techniques is that the neural networks have more general functional forms. Kolmogorov's Mapping Neural Network Existence Theorem further proves that a three-layer neural network can exactly implement any continuous mapping [3]. This result gives hope that, with the proper connections among neurons, the network is itself able to approximate any mapping of practical interest to any desired degree of accuracy. Another advantage is neurocomputing's parallel distributed processing (PDP) ability to construct an unknown mapping from the tabulated output values at random input points [4]. The PDP models assume that information processing takes place through the interactions of a large

number of simple processing neurons, each sending excitatory and inhibitory signals to other neurons in the learning procedure. This corresponds to a numerical recursive procedure for computing the weight changes of connectivity between any two neurons. Finally, a mapping can be in general represented by several weight matrices that constitute the pattern of connectivity from input to output.

II. DATA GENERATION AND PREPROCESSING

Consider Figure (1) below, which shows a rectangular micro strip patch antenna of length L , width W resting on a substrate of height h . The co-ordinate axis is selected such that the length is along the x direction, width is along the y direction and the height is along the z direction. The design of a patch requires height of the substrate and dielectric constant of the material, from these two we can calculate rest all the parameters. The dimensions of the patch along its length will be extended because of fringing fields on each end by a distance ΔL , which is given empirically by Hammerstad as:-

$$\Delta L = 0.124h \frac{\epsilon_{reff} + 0.3}{\epsilon_{eff} - 0.258} \left[\frac{\frac{w}{h} + 0.264}{\frac{w}{h} + 0.8} \right] \text{----- (1)}$$

$$\epsilon_{reff} = \frac{\epsilon_r + 1}{2} + \frac{\epsilon_r - 1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{12h}{w} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

is the effective dielectric constant of the substrate.

The effective length of the patch L_{eff} now becomes:-

$$L_{eff} = L + \Delta L \text{----- (2)}$$

For a given resonance frequency f_0 , the effective length is given by:

$$L_{eff} = \frac{c}{2f_0 \sqrt{\epsilon_{reff}}} \text{---- (3)}$$

For a rectangular Micro strip patch antenna, the resonance frequency for any TM_{mn} mode is given by James and Hall:-

$$f_0 = \frac{c}{2\sqrt{\epsilon_{reff}}} \sqrt{\left[\left(\frac{m}{L} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{n}{W} \right)^2 \right]} \text{----- (4)}$$

Where m and n are modes along L and W respectively. For efficient radiation, the width W is given by

$$W = \frac{c}{2f_0 \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon_r + 1}{2}}} \text{----- (5)}$$

Now we have taken l , w , h , ϵ_r as the input parameters and we have trained back propagation algorithm to calculate resonant frequency of the patch. For this we have taken one input layer, one hidden layer and one output layer. Input layer consists of the above parameters, we formed two matrices to assign random weights one for hidden to input layer and the other for output to hidden layer. The architecture of KBNN is shown in fig.2. For the present work we considered Input layer neurons are 4, Hidden layer neurons are 20 and output layer neuron is one.

Figure 1. Rectangular patch antenna

Input layer hidden layer output layer

Fig 2. KBNN architecture

III. ALGORITHM

Step 1: Initialize weights

Step 2: submit input pattern and compute layer's response.

Step 3: Compute cycle error. Step 4: Calculate errors.

Step 5: Adjust weights of output layer. Step 6: Adjust weights of hidden layer.

Step 7: If more patterns are there then start new training step.

Step 8: If Step 7 is false then compare error with error tolerance if it is less then end or else start new training cycle.

We have considered sigmoid function to calculate output and lambda in sigmoid function is considered as 0.5 for the training and testing data. Error tolerance we considered is 0.001 and we are successful in achieving it. Length, width, height are in cm.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Leng th	Widt h	Heig ht	ϵ_r	Freque ncy	Output	Error
0.22	0.95	0.22	0.2	0.998	0.997	0.001
0.22	0.80	0.31	0.2	0.8323	0.8313	0.0009
0.24	0.71	0.41	0.2	0.6711	0.6701	0.0009
0.24	0.57	0.51	0.6	0.6202	0.6193	0.0008
0.24	0.50	0.51	0.8	0.6255	0.6246	0.0009
0.32	0.51	0.80	0.2	0.3680	0.369	0.0009
0.44	0.41	0.80	0.6	0.2863	0.2873	0.0009
0.58	0.50	0.51	0.8	0.2779	0.279	0.0009
0.66	0.35	0.61	1	0.2324	0.2334	0.0009
0.78	0.38	0.90	0.6	0.1565	0.1576	0.0009
0.98	0.52	0.80	0.2	0.1223	0.1233	0.0009
1	0.71	0.41	0.4	0.1723	0.1733	0.0009
1	0.29	0.90	0.8	0.1269	0.1279	0.0009

There are many algorithms in neural networks to apply for a specific problem but choosing optimum one is always a difficult task. Error back propagation training algorithm (EBPTA) is most widely used one for calculation of resonant frequency or length, width of the micro strip patch antenna from other parameters etc. The proposed algorithm calculates the resonant frequency or length or width efficiently compared to other standard MLP algorithms. While choosing lambda and eta care must be taken because these two parameters decides the speed of the algorithm, means if we choose lambda 0.1 to 0.4 or 0.6 to 0.9 and eta >1 then speed is less, on the other hand lambda is 0.5 and eta >1 speed is high. Recently an optimized value has been presented in [5].

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper we have trained back propagation algorithm for the efficient design of micro strip patch antenna. We have used 700 samples for training and 500 samples for testing; using length, width, height and dielectric constant of the substrate we have calculated resonant frequency. This can be used as a CAD model to calculate resonant frequency of either square or circular patch antenna.

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